

Studies on Emulsions of Bordeaux mixture, Nickel Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux in Presence of Some Indian Gums

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Bordeaux mixture which gives better protection to vine yards from the mildew in the form of sprays and dusts and is also applied to agricultural crops, particularly potatoes, field grown plants and green house plants, has been tried as emulsion stabiliser. The effect of some Indian gums on the stability of emulsions produced by this agent has also been studied by the size frequency analysis of King and Mukherjee. In the hope of finding an emulsifying agent superior to Bordeaux mixture the work has been extended to some related compounds e.g., Nickel Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux.

IN continuation to our previous work on some copper compounds¹² as emulsion stabilisers in the form of fungicides, the work has been extended to Bordeaux mixture and some other related compounds. According to Millardet and Gayon⁹, Bordeaux mixture gives better protection to vineyards from the mildew for which sulphur compounds, which were used in the past were ineffective.

Numerous workers^{2,5,8,9} have investigated the chemical reactions which take place between the calcium hydroxide and copper sulphate in solution.

Pickering¹³ indicated that with the ratio of copper sulphate to calcium oxide 1 : 0.166, a double salt having the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]_3 \cdot \text{CuSO}_4$ was formed; with a ratio of 1 : 0.181, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]_4 \cdot \text{CuSO}_4$; 1 : 0.20, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]_9 \cdot \text{CuSO}_4$; 1 : 0.269, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]_9 \cdot \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{CuSO}_4$; 1 : 1, $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]_9 \cdot \text{CuSO}_4$; $[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2]_3 \cdot \text{CaSO}_4$; was formed.

More recent and more accurate work along the similar lines has been done by Martin⁵.

Experimental

Preparation of Bordeaux Mixtures and size frequency analysis of emulsions :

Many workers^{2,8,13} have investigated the physical methods of preparing Bordeaux mixture. Butler⁸ ascertained that the physical state of the precipitate of Bordeaux mixture depended to a large extent on the dilution of the salts and the manner in which they were brought together. Several copper lime dusts have been reported from time to time, using copper sulphate and calcium hydroxide in intimate mixture. In this work, however, Pickering's¹³ method for preparing Bordeaux mixture using lime and copper sulphate has been followed.

In a similar manner Nickel Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux have been prepared. The fresh precipitates so obtained have been used as emulsifying

agents alone and in combination with some less common gums. The gums were purified as described earlier⁷. The emulsions were prepared at 30° by King and Mukherjee's¹ method using two fixed ratios of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CaO alone and then by adding fixed amounts of previously used gums¹² keeping the ratio of oil to water as 20 : 80, so that the emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be sprayed easily. Emulsions were also prepared with Nickel Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux respectively keeping the same ratios as in case of above reported Bordeaux mixture. The stability coefficients were computed from the data on the specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described by Mukherjee and Shukla⁶⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

Liquids of low surface tension, such as oils and possibly their emulsions, readily penetrate through the very small apertures such as stomata (breathing pores) of leaves and the tracheal openings of insects, where liquids of higher surface tension, such as water, cannot enter. Oils penetrate leaves principally through the stomata¹⁴, but entrance also occurs through the epidermis^{3,4,10}. Young and Morris¹¹ has confirmed that the rate of penetration is largely dependent on viscosity, modified by field temperatures. Oils applied on the under side leaf only penetrate more rapidly than on the upper side because of the greater abundance of the stomata on the lower side.

Microscopic studies of oil within a living leaf have shown that the lighter lubricating oils and kerosene move through the water tubes or tracheids as tiny globules of oil. More viscous oils (100 to 120 seconds Saybolt) clog these tubes and prevent the oil from being translocated, leaving it fixed in the leaf blade.

Kerosenes may enter the leaf structure, both through the stomata and the epidermis, within a few

hours, whereas the period of penetration of lubricating oils of viscosities of 100 to 110 seconds Saybolt may extend over days.

The case of translocation of very light oils within the structure of leaf and twig is also closely related to the viscosity of the oil.

In accordance with the above view point a large number of emulsions of kerosene oil stabilised by Bordeaux mixture and modified Bordeaux mixtures were prepared and size frequency analysis was done immediately and after different intervals thereafter. The results are too numerous to quote in full but a representative selection is given in Table 1. The number of emulsions refer to the summarised results in Table 3, the suffix to the length of time in weeks,

which elapsed between emulsification and analysis. In all these cases emulsions had been homogenised.

The results of these tables are all concerned with kerosene oil emulsions. It is interesting that in all cases the degree of dispersion of the freshly prepared emulsion is great.

In case of Copper Bordeaux stabilised emulsion the initial dispersion varied between 3μ (3.47%) to 25μ (0.88%). The percentage of 5μ particles was maximum (87.37%). There was gradual increase in the size of the particle globules in the course of 2 months. Rapid coarsening took place just after 4 weeks storage. The separation of oil started on the 3rd day (1.0%) which reached to 6.35% after storage for 6 weeks.

TABLE 1(A)—PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF OIL DROPLETS OF DIFFERENT SIZES IN HOMOGENISED EMULSIONS (INDICES OVER THE EMULSION NUMBER DENOTE THE NUMBER OF WEEKS THAT HAVE ELAPSED)

Mean diameter (μ)	Emulsion no....	0	3/7	1	2	3	4	6	8
		83	83	83	83	83	83	38	83
2		3.30	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3		2.31	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4		1.98	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
5		62.05	62.08	58.94	52.91	50.84	42.49	—	32.72
10		9.90	11.00	11.00	12.73	13.36	16.61	—	18.99
15		7.26	8.17	8.41	9.28	9.35	9.84	—	11.66
20		6.60	7.86	7.74	7.95	8.01	9.23	—	10.66
25		3.63	3.67	5.82	6.53	6.95	7.38	—	9.99
30		1.98	2.83	3.24	5.04	5.34	6.15	—	6.66
35		0.99	2.51	2.94	3.18	3.21	5.23	—	5.99
40		—	1.88	1.94	2.38	2.94	3.07	—	3.33
45		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Free oil separation (p.c.)		nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	—	nil
Agent		Nickel Bordeaux	(Calcium oxide + Nickel sulphate) 0.166 : 1						

TABLE 1(B)

Mean diameter (μ)	Emulsion no....	0	3/7	1	2	3	4	6	8	
		76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	
2		0.81	0.41	—	—	—	—	—	—	
3		0.91	0.83	0.97	—	—	—	—	—	
4		0.81	0.83	0.97	—	—	—	—	—	
5		88.12	86.69	83.15	81.80	79.11	75.86	69.68	67.33	
10		7.34	8.16	9.75	11.53	13.45	15.00	17.17	17.36	
15		1.63	1.83	2.34	2.46	2.57	3.50	4.77	4.96	
20		0.32	0.84	1.07	1.54	1.83	2.27	4.00	4.20	
25		—	0.41	0.97	1.07	1.22	1.25	1.91	2.29	
30		—	—	0.78	0.84	0.97	1.12	1.33	1.53	
35		—	—	—	0.76	0.85	1.00	1.14	1.33	
40		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
Free oil separation (p.c.)		nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	
Agent		Bordeaux Mixture (CaO : CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O) + 0.1% Dhak gum 0.166 : 1								

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The dispersion in case of 1 : 1 ratio (emulsion no. 79) was finer as compared to the ratio 1 : 0.166 (emulsion no. 75). Thus the percentage of fine particles from 1μ to 4μ was greater on the 1st day and the maximum number of particles of 5μ (88.24%) were present. The particles upto 10μ size only were seen on the 1st day. Coarsening took place just after 1 week storage and the distribution ranged from 5μ (82.18%) to 30μ (1.27%). After eight weeks storage time, the size of the globules ranged from 5μ (36.57%) to 40μ (3.45%). The separation of oil was smaller as compared to the previous system. The separation of oil started after 3rd day (0.05%) which increased to 5% on 2 months storage.

Combination of Dhak gum, Bel gum and Katira gum produced somewhat finer emulsions as compared to Copper Bordeaux alone. Coarsening was not much in these cases. In case of Dhak and Bel gum no separation of oil was detected even after 2 months time with both the ratios (1 : 1 and 1 : 0.166). But separation of oil took place in case of Katira combination, the extent of separation of oil was much less as compared to Copper Bordeaux stabilised emulsions.

Nickel Bordeaux stabilised emulsions come in between the Copper Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux stabilised emulsions so far as the initial particle sizes

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC AREA AND SEPARATION OF OIL FROM EMULSIONS ON VARIOUS INTERVALS OF TIME. SPECIFIC AREA IN SQ. CM/GM OIL (ALL VALUES $\times 10^3$)
After

Emulsion no.	Stabiliser Ratio	Immediate	After						
			3/7 week	1 week	2 weeks	3 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks	8 weeks
A. <i>Bordeaux Mixture</i> ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$) stabilised emulsions									
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO} + \text{Gum}$									
75	1 : 0.166 alone	11.46 (nil)	8.45 (1.0)	4.04 (1.75)	3.48 (2.25)	3.37 (2.85)	3.67 (5.35)	1.98 (6.35)	—
76	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	9.27 (nil)	7.87 (nil)	5.47 (nil)	4.47 (nil)	4.18 (nil)	4.07 (nil)	3.98 (nil)	3.25 (nil)
77	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	9.53 (nil)	7.94 (nil)	5.71 (nil)	4.76 (nil)	4.39 (nil)	3.42 (nil)	3.21 (nil)	—
78	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	12.22 (nil)	—	9.79 (nil)	5.47 (0.25)	4.83 (1.50)	3.61 (2.00)	2.36 (3.60)	2.13 (4.40)
79	1 : 1 alone	12.36 (nil)	11.53 (0.05)	9.20 (1.15)	5.79 (1.80)	—	3.53 (3.50)	2.45 (4.5)	2.00 (5.00)
80	1 : 1 + 0.1% Dhak gum	11.97 (nil)	11.07 (nil)	10.72 (nil)	10.54 (nil)	8.98 (nil)	7.62 (nil)	—	7.11 (nil)
81	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	13.15 (nil)	10.93 (nil)	—	9.64 (nil)	8.90 (nil)	8.15 (nil)	—	5.75 (nil)
82	1 : 1 + 0.1% Katira gum	15.03 (nil)	13.87 (0.05)	9.65 (1.50)	—	3.53 (2.0)	2.89 (2.85)	2.71 (3.20)	2.28 (3.50)
B. <i>Nickel Bordeaux</i> ($\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$) stabilised emulsions									
$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO} + \text{Gum}$									
83	1 : 0.166 alone	4.04 (nil)	3.73 (nil)	2.84 (nil)	2.76 (nil)	2.70 (nil)	2.64 (nil)	—	2.11 (nil)
84	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	9.27 (nil)	8.19 (nil)	7.68 (nil)	6.82 (nil)	5.87 (nil)	5.13 (nil)	—	3.23 (nil)
85	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	4.50 (nil)	3.33 (nil)	3.07 (nil)	2.72 (nil)	2.69 (nil)	2.48 (nil)	—	2.63 (nil)
86	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	I m m e d i a t e l y B r o k e n							
87	1 : 1 alone	7.20 (nil)	6.50 (nil)	4.28 (nil)	3.28 (nil)	3.16 (0.50)	2.75 (0.75)	2.72 (2.0)	—
88	1 : + 0.1% Dhak gum	7.00 (nil)	—	6.47 (nil)	6.24 (nil)	6.07 (nil)	5.40 (nil)	5.24 (nil)	4.94 (nil)
89	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	3.90 (nil)	3.11 (nil)	3.00 (nil)	2.99 (nil)	2.99 (nil)	2.89 (nil)	—	2.09 (nil)
90	1 : 1 + 0.1% Katira gum	I m m e d i a t e l y B r o k e n							

Table 2—(Contd.)

Emulsion no.	Stabiliser Ratio	Immediate	After						
			3/7 week	1 week	2 weeks	3 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks	8 weeks
C. Zinc Bordeaux (ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O : CaO) stabilised emulsions									
ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O : CaO + Gum									
91	1 : 0.166 alone	6.62 (nil)	5.16 (1.0)	3.05 (1.75)	2.81 (2.35)	2.41 (2.85)	2.30 (3.85)	2.05 (5.35)	1.87 (6.35)
92	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	3.90 (nil)	3.07 (nil)	3.02 (nil)	3.00 (nil)	2.97 (nil)	2.94 (nil)	2.86 (nil)	2.76 (nil)
93	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	3.44 (nil)	3.05 (nil)	2.94 (nil)	2.94 (nil)	2.85 (nil)	2.08 (nil)	2.00 (nil)	—
94	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	7.93 (nil)	6.50 (0.25)	5.19 (0.75)	3.98 (2.75)	—	2.30 (4.25)	2.16 (4.75)	1.93 (6.00)
95	1 : 1 alone	4.82 (nil)	3.73 (nil)	3.58 (nil)	3.19 (0.50)	2.94 (1.50)	2.48 (3.50)	2.37 (4.00)	1.99 (5.00)
96	1 : 1 + 0.1% Dhak gum	3.10 (nil)	3.09 (nil)	3.09 (nil)	3.07 (nil)	—	3.03 (nil)	2.90 (nil)	2.81 (nil)
97	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	4.58 (nil)	—	4.50 (nil)	4.43 (nil)	4.35 (nil)	4.17 (nil)	4.14 (nil)	3.86 (nil)
98	1 : 1 + 0.1% Katira gum	10.81 (nil)	8.65 (nil)	—	4.64 (0.50)	2.99 (2.00)	2.58 (2.50)	2.43 (3.50)	2.06 (4.00)

(Quantity in parenthesis being the percentage of oil separation on a particular day).

are concerned. The globule size remained fine even after storage of 2 months. The particle size varied from 1 μ to 40 μ from the very beginning of preparation to the end of two months storage time, but the percentage of fine particles 5 μ , 10 μ and 15 μ was as high as 46.53%, 20.17% and 10.86% respectively even after 2 months in case of 1 : 1 ratio. The effect of addition of gums was similar to the case of Copper Bordeaux combinations. The single substance as well as the combination with gum (Dhak and Bel) produced peculiar type of emulsions where there was no separation of oil even after two months storage. Combination of Katira gum proved to be detrimental as the emulsions produced were broken immediately after preparation and complete separation of oil took place immediately.

From the point of view of emulsion stability, the distribution of various droplets sizes discussed above is less important than the variation of the total interface with time. In Table 2 the values of total area of interface per gm of oil as calculated from the size frequency analysis of emulsions of different ages, have been collected. The figures in brackets indicate the percentage of the total oil which has separated as free oil in each case.

It will be seen that in the finest and most stable emulsions, the area of interface decreases regularly with time and that in the less stable emulsions, the rate of decay appears to be greater.

In Fig. 1 the log values of specific surfaces are plotted against time as abscissa on graph paper for several emulsions to illustrate the agreement between

the data on the change of specific surface with time and the exponential hypothesis as earlier¹². The

Fig. 1

lines were determined by fitting the data to the equation :

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient and K = stability coefficient, by the method of least squares.

The curves representing the degradation of the emulsions are all linear, hence a measure of the slope

gives a quantitative comparison of stability. Accordingly the slope of each curve has been measured and divided by the graphically determined initial interface to give the rate of decrease per unit area of interface. This is termed the instability factor and is defined as the decrease of each square centimeter of fresh emulsion interface per day. The reciprocal of this is a direct measure of emulsion stability (K) and is given in Table 3. It can be seen from the data of Table 3 that Copper Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux gave emulsions which had the stability coefficients nearly of the same order (13.98 and 14.37). Nickel Bordeaux produced emulsion with stability coefficient 27.58 which was stabler in comparison to the other two. When the ratio of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$ was increased from 1 : 0.166 to 1 : 1 the emulsions produced were definitely more stable thus giving the stability coefficients as 21.49, 28.30, 20.00 respectively.

The stability coefficients were improved nearly in all the cases when Dhak gum was added with the individual Bordeaux mixture. Combinations of Nickel Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux with Dhak gum gave very stable emulsions as is evident from the stability coefficient values of emulsions Nos. 84, 88, 92 and 96 respectively.

Addition of Bel gum improved the emulsion stabilities, the increase being more in case of Copper Bordeaux combination and Zinc Bordeaux combination with Bel gum, as can be seen from the data on stability of these in Table 3.

Katira gum although improved the emulsion stability coefficient values when used in combination with Copper Bordeaux and Zinc Bordeaux respectively but the increase was not much as can be seen by comparing the stability coefficient values of emulsion Nos. 75, 79, with 78, 82 and those of emulsion Nos. 91, 95 with 94 and 98 respectively.

On the other hand addition of Katira gum to Nickel Bordeaux had a deteriorating effect on the stability of emulsions. These combinations could not produce stable emulsions, and the emulsions produced were broken immediately after preparation; thus addition of Katira gum produced some antagonistic effect.

In all the three cases of Bordeaux mixtures described above the ratio of the calcium oxide had a marked effect on the emulsion stability. The stability coefficient values were improved from the corresponding stability coefficient values when the ratio of CuSO_4 , NiSO_4 or ZnSO_4 to CaO was 1 : 0.166.

According to Pickering¹³ and others the fungicidal action of Bordeaux mixture depends upon the liberation of normal copper sulphate by action of atmospheric carbon dioxide. A certain time elapses before the fungicidal action commences because the basic sulphate of copper is not attacked by carbon dioxide until all the basic sulphate of calcium has been decomposed. The delay in the action of fungicide would, therefore, be less, provided only sufficient amount of lime has been used to produce basic sulphates of copper alone instead of the double sulphates

of copper and calcium. Accordingly the emulsions stabilised by various salts in which the ratio of lime was not in excess of 1 equivalent have higher insecticidal value. If, however, the amount of lime used in the precipitation of Bordeaux mixture was greater than one equivalent, the insecticidal efficiency will be almost destroyed because the excess of basic calcium sulphate formed will retard the action of atmospheric carbon dioxide to liberate soluble copper-sulphate which is so necessary for fungicidal action to come into play.

Further, if lime is used as precipitant, one cannot use the higher concentrations of copper sulphate as well, as they yield emulsions with very low stability.

TABLE 3—DATA FOR 20% KEROSENE OIL EMULSIONS

Emulsion no.	Stabiliser Ratio	Stability coefficient values $\times 10^3$	Graphically determined initial specific area [σ_0]
A : Bordeaux Mixture ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$) stabilised emulsions ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO} + \text{Gum}$)			
75	1 : 0.166 (alone)	13.98	7.41 cm^2/g
76	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	29.39	6.76
77	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	22.12	7.08
78	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	19.85	9.33
79	1 : 1 (alone)	21.49	10.96
80	1 : 1 + 0.1% Dhak gum	72.66	11.48
81	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	66.76	11.76
82	1 : 1 + 0.1% Katira gum	22.48	13.49
B. Nickel Bordeaux ($\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$) stabilised emulsions ($\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO} + \text{Gum}$)			
83	1 : 0.166 (alone)	27.58	3.31 cm^2/g
84	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	42.43	8.91
85	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	42.37	3.39
86	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	Broken	—
87	1 : 1 (alone)	28.30	5.49
88	1 : 1 + 0.1% Dhak gum	94.28	6.60
89	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	24.78	3.47
90	1 : 0.1% Katira gum	Broken	—
C. Zinc Bordeaux ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO}$) stabilised emulsions ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{CaO} + \text{Gum}$)			
91	1 : 0.166 (alone)	14.37	4.17 cm^2/g
92	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Dhak gum	63.20	3.16
93	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Bel gum	18.47	3.16
94	1 : 0.166 + 0.1% Katira gum	16.36	5.89
95	1 : 1 (alone)	20.00	3.80
96	1 : 1 + 0.1% Dhak gum	70.22	3.09
97	1 : 1 + 0.1% Bel gum	87.80	4.57
98	1 : 1 + 0.1% Katira gum	18.47	7.76

Bordeaux mixture is a fairly good emulsifier and this led the authors to prepare similar compounds using NiSO_4 and ZnSO_4 in combination with calcium hydroxide as a precipitant.

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